

On Mechanical Fastening in Graphite Epoxy Composite

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ABSTRACT

In composite material structures, components must be joined such that the overall structure performs its function and retains its structural integrity, while suffering no or little weight penalty due to joining. Otherwise the many advantages of utilizing composites rather than metals can be negated or reduced.

Although adhesive bonding is often a preferred method of joining, mechanical fasteners must be used in many many cases, e.g., when access to the interior of the composite structure is necessary, or for those components which must be replaced periodically.

For the design of rational and optimized structures involving mechanical fasteners, extensive experimentation is necessary to develop a data bank for design and analysis. In this paper, data is presented for two types of graphite composites, T300/5209 and AS3501, quasi-isotropic, $[0,45,90-45]_{2g}$, flat specimens, with the fasteners torqued or untorqued, at room temperature and ambient humidity.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

As stated above, the testing utilized specimens of sixteen ply, quasi-isotropic graphite epoxy, which were provided by the NASA Langley Research Center. Each specimen was four inches in length, one and one half inches in width with a quarter inch diameter hole drilled equidistant from each edge, and centered three quarters of an inch from one end, as depicted in Fig. 1.

In what follows, s is the average distance from the edge of the hole to the side of the specimen; e is the distance from the edge of the hole to the end of the specimen; d is the hole diameter. To change e/d ratios and s/d ratios, the specimens were machined utilizing a diamond saw. The range of ratios utilized were limited by the prefabricated specimen dimensions.

A test fixture shown in Fig. 2 was designed and fabricated. Standard friction grips were used to hold the last pieces in an Instron test machine. At the end with a hole loading plates were used which had one-quarter-inch holes

through which to insert a bolt. The clamping action of the bolt on the specimen was varied from zero inch-lbs of torque up to fifty inch pounds of torque to investigate its effect. Testing was performed at a displacement rate of 0.1 cm/min only. The load and displacement were recorded on a standard x-y plotter.

The variables investigated were the e/d ratios (2.5, 2.0, 1.5 and 1.0), the s/d ratios (2.5, 2.0 and 1.0), and the amount of bolt torque (0 and 25 in-lbs reported on herein). A minimum of three replicates for each combination was performed, resulting in at least seventy-two tests for each material system.

FAILURE MODES

The three modes of failure that occurred were bearing failure, cleavage failure and net tension failure as depicted in Fig. 3.

Bearing failure involves local failure in contact with the bolt such that an elongation of the bolt hold occurs. It is characterized by a sharp but small unloading on the load-displacement graph, as well as a change in slope upon subsequence loading. Although bearing failure occurred in almost all of the non-torqued specimens, as well as some torqued specimens, it is not catastrophic, and usually the specimen continues to withstand considerably more load, as the deflection continues, before catastrophic failure occurs at the ultimate load. Thus bearing "failure" may not be as serious in some structural applications as it is in others.

Cleavage failure is characterized by a single surface extensive damage parallel to the loading, from the bolt hole to the end of the specimen, such that the bolt disengages itself from the specimen in a catastrophic manner, as the load goes to zero. It is distinctive from shear out failure, which has two parallel fracture surfaces.

Net tension failure is also catastrophic in that two failure surfaces progress from each side of the bolt hold, ostensibly perpendicular to the load direction to each side of the specimen. The bolt and the specimen end are thus separated from the rest of the specimen.

DATA ANALYSIS

T300/5209

1. Bearing Failure Load vs. Side Distance Ratio with Torque at 0. The maximum failure load occurred at an $s/d = 1$ and $e/d = 2.0$. For all e/d except an $e/d = 1$, the failure loads dropped off for increasing s/d . The failure loads for an $e/d = 1$ increased with the highest failure load of an $s/d = 2.5$.
2. Bearing Failure Load vs. Side Distance Ratio with Torque at 25 in-lbs. The torque has a marked effect on the failure values, compared to 0 torque. In all cases except one the failure values increased, some significantly so. The torqued pieces show a polarization if failure behavior. The two highest e/d ratios show a downwards trend as the s/d is increased, while the two lowest e/d ratios show an upwards behavior for increasing s/d . The highest failure load was at the two largest e/d ratios of an s/d of 2.0.
3. Net Tension Failure Load vs. Side Distance Ratio with Torque at 0 and 25 in-lbs. The zero torque net tension failure only occurs at the lowest s/d , and the failure value is independent of e/d values.
For 25 in-lbs torque the net tension failure model was prevalent and the results indicated linear trends. All the e/d evidenced a monotonically increasing behavior for increasing s/d . The maximum failure load was given by an $e/d = 2.5$ and $s/d = 2.5$.
4. Cleavage Failure Load vs. Side Distance Ratio with Torque at 0 and

25 in-lbs. For the zero torque the cleavage failure mode rarely occurred and then only for the lowest value of e/d .

When the torque was increased to 25 in-lbs. the cleavage failure mode was more prevalent but some what sporadic. Only for values of s/d of 2.0 and 2.5 did the test pieces cleavage, and as the subscripts by the symbols of the e/d at s/d of 2.0 indicate sometimes only one piece failed there. The maximum value was for an e/d of 2.5 at an s/d of 2.5.

AS 3501

1. Bearing Failure Load vs. Side Distance Ratio with Torque Equal to 0. Here, a spurious behavior occurred. The two lowest s/d show opposing trends with initial and final values for increasing s/d to be not much different. On the other hand, the two highest e/d show linear monotonically increasing failure values for increasing s/d . The maximum value was at an $e/d = 2.0$ and s/d of 2.5.

2. Bearing Failure Load vs. Side Distance Ratio with Torque at 25 in-lbs. With the torque at 25 in-lbs, only two e/d values yielded results for all three values of s/d , and even these did not occur in all test pieces. The maximum failure value was at an e/d of 2.0 and s/d of 2.5.

3. Net Tension Failure Load vs. Side Distance Ratio with Torque Equal to 0. With no torque, net tension certainly is not the dominant failure mode. The only reliable maximum failure value, which is still lower than the bearing ($T = 0$) maximum, is at an e/d of 2.5 and s/d of 1.0.

4. Net Tension Failure Load vs. Side Distance Ratio with Torque at 25 in-lbs. When a torque of 25 in-lbs is applied to the test pieces the net tension failure mode was prevalent again showing a monotonically increasing linear trend for all e/d except the $e/d = 1$, for increasing s/d . The maximum failure value was for an e/d of 2.5 and $s/d = 2.5$

5. Cleavage Failure vs. Side Distance Ratio with Torque at 0 and 25 in-lbs. With or without torque, the cleavage mode does not occur often and then only for the two lowest e/d ratios. No cleavage occurred at the lowest s/d . The maximum failure load for the untorqued specimens was at an e/d of 1.5 and s/d of 2.5. The maximum (reliable) failure load for the torqued specimens was also at an e/d of 1.5 and s/d of 2.5. It should be noted that the torqued pieces showed higher failure values.

CONCLUSIONS

1. It is seen that it is a necessity to do a painstaking, indepth, testing procedure for each material system even though the fiber orientation and laminate stacking sequence is exactly the same.

2. The 5209 gives the highest bearing failure load compared to the 3501, at an e/d of 2.0 and s/d of 1.0 as compared to the 3501, at an e/d of 2.0 and s/d of 2.5.

3. The results show that when both material systems are subjected to a 25 in-lbs torque they are able to carry a significantly greater load before failure in each combination of e/d and s/d . In addition, the trends differ.

4. The 3501 had higher failure values than the 5209 for the torqued specimens. The maximum of the 3501 was at an e/d of 2.0 and s/d of 2.5, where as the 5209 maximum was at an e/d of 2.5 and s/d of 2.0.

5. Net tension vs. s/d , 0 torque. The results indicate that the 5209 system experienced net tension failure at a higher value than the 3501 for all e/d at an s/d of 1.0. The 5209 did not evidence any net tension failure for any other s/d ratios where as the 3501 did.

Net Tension vs. s/d , 25 in-lbs Torque.

6. The 5209 system showed superior net tension failure values over the 3501 in each instance of e/d and s/d combination for 25 in-lbs torque.

7. One conclusion that could be made is that for net tension failure for both systems with 25 in-lbs torque the best design is at high e/d and high s/d ratios, within the ratios tested.

8. Cleavage failure, except for one instance, always occurred in conjunction with net tension failure for the 5209 system.

9. Cleavage failure, except for two instances, always occurred in conjunction with net tension failure for the 3501 system, whenever cleavage failure occurred at all.

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Table 1. Test Results for T300/5209 Specimens.

Torque (in-lbs)	s/d	e/d = 2.5			e/d = 2.0			e/d = 1.5			e/d						
		No. of Tests	B	NT	CL	No. of Tests	B	NT	CL	No. of Tests	B	NT	CL	No. of Tests	B	NT	CL
T = 0	1.0	3	748 ⁷ /3 ^{**}	763/2	--	3	770/1	770/1	--	3	725/8	745/4	--	3	^{***} 745/2	758/3	^{***} 758
	2.0	3	740/1	--	--	3	730/3	--	--	3	768/2	--	--	3	717/3	--	--
	2.5	3	731/3	--	--	4	620/7	--	--	4	638/4	--	--	4	745/4	--	774/1
T = 25	1.0	3	832/5	902/2	--	3	^{***} 843/1	867/4	--	3	826/3	848/3	--	3	804/3	827/3	--
	2.0	3	937/20	1410/1	^{***} 1410	3	923/36	1298/2	1298/2	3	785/3	1094/4	^{***} 1094	3	^{***} 726/2	^{***} 892	892/3
	2.5	4	818/4	1453/4	1453/4	3	843/4	1338/2	1338/2	5	885/4	1240/3	1240/3	4	823/2	^{***} 892	898/3

*Failure load in lbs.

** $\left(\frac{\text{Standard deviation}}{\text{Failure load}} \times 100 \right)$ in %.

*** No. of failures that occurred in this mode, if different from no. of specimens tested.

Table 2. Test Results for AS3501 Specimens.

Torque (in-lbs)	s/d	e/d = 2.5				e/d = 2.0				e/d = 1.5				e/d			
		No. of Tests	B	NT	CL	No. of Tests	B	NT	CL	No. of Tests	B	NT	CL	No. of Tests	B	NT	CL
T = 0	1.0	3	536 ^{**} /14 ^{**}	696/6	--	3	***558/8	690/3	--	3	649/3	663/4	--	3	***635	663/3	--
	2.0	3	689/9	--	--	3	673/3	--	--	3	716/5	***767	***767	3	607/7	***720/1	***720/1
	2.5	3	734/3	--	--	3	750/6	***810	--	3	647/4	--	803/7	3	668/1	--	663/1
T = 25	1.0	3	***761	845/7	--	3	--	858/4	--	3	***788	827/5	--	3	***713/1	757/2	--
	2.0	3	1133/6	1232/2	--	3	***1028/9	1177/3	--	3	***860	937/4	***961/1	3	--	691/1	691/1
	2.5	3	1097/13	1324/2	--	3	1160/1	1220/3	***1230	3	946/4	1013/1	1013/1	3	--	798/6	798/6

*Failure load in lbs.

** $\left(\frac{\text{Standard deviation}}{\text{Failure load}} \times 100 \right)$ in %.

***No. of failures that occurred in this mode, if different from no. of specimens tested.

$$\frac{S}{D} = \frac{E_L + E_R}{2D}, \quad \frac{e}{D}$$

FIGURE 1. SPECIMEN NOMENCLATURE

FIGURE 2. TEST FIXTURE

BEARING

NET TENSION

CLEAVAGE

FIGURE 3. TYPES OF FAILURE